

The Discourse of Patriarchy, Gender, and Violence in Pakistani English Print Media: A Corpus-Based Study

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Abstract: Pakistani society is firmly characterized by patriarchal values. These values determine the social position of women in Pakistani society. Gender, ideology and restrictive codes of behavior are used to exert control over women and female virtue and honor are associated with family honor. These patriarchal values are mainly the fountain source of violence against women (VAW). VAW includes honor killing, sexual harassment, marital rape, forced marriage, rape, domestic violence, acid burning, etc. The present study aims at investigating the sufferings of women in Pakistan, and the nature of these sufferings, and how men resort to patriarchal norms to perpetuate the subjugation of women. The patriarchal system needs violence for its existence. The present study adopted a mixed methods approach to analyze data collected from various English newspapers of Pakistan from 2017 to 2018. The findings conclude that men use all types of violence to ensure women's subjugation. It has also discovered that structural violence is also responsible for women's plight. To eradicate VAW, women have to be empowered socially, politically, and economically.

Key words: discourse, violence, domestic violence gender, patriarch, corpora

1. Introduction

Violence against girls and women is believed to be a violation of basic human rights. Violence against women is present in one form or the other in every society. Women belonging to any segment of society become victims of it at some stage of their lives. Women face various kind of violence which includes women battering, sexual harassment, psychological, emotional violence, threats and acid burning and so on. Patriarchal values are deeply rooted in Pakistani society. These patriarchal values determine women's subordinate status in society. Various institutional and religious restrictive codes, abnormal and inhuman cultural traditions and practices, female modesty, and ideological norms are used to exert masculine control over women. Gender-based violence is a serious issue in the country and is on the rise every year (Aurat Foundation and Human Rights Commission of Pakistan, 2021).

Gender-based violence reflects a patriarchal social system. Men use violence as a social tool to subordinate women (Walby, 1990). Men also use violence as a weapon to assert their authority. Therefore, feminists believe that patriarchy is a straight-away cause of gender-based violence. Feminist literature defines patriarchy in several ways. Some use the term patriarchy to refer to distinguish power of men over women (Hartman, 1979; Millet, 1969). Some refer to patriarchy as a male ideology embedded in their psychology (Rothman, 2016.) and Mukoro (2021) emphasizes that it stems from biological sex differences and the sexual system of power seeks male

dominance in society, while Ataken (2014) argues that its foundations rest on economic relations of production. Patriarchy is an expression of the institutionalized dominance and power of men over women and children (Learner, 1986). Learner (1986) also argues that male dominance is systematic and the institutionalized and is visible in every important institution of society. Patriarchy is a set of social values, structures, and practices that men employ to subjugate, suppress, exploit, and control women (Walby, 1990). She identified six structures of patriarchy. These structures comprise housework, sexuality, paid work, violence, and culture. Men use these structures to control women. Hunnicut (2009) states that patriarchal systems work at two levels: (i) macro level (religion, market, law, bureaucracy, and government, (ii) micro level: (relations with intimate partners, organizations, and families). Feminist theories mainly created the concept of patriarchy to construe the continuation of male dominance in the modern societies. The feminist theories include Marxist, Radical, Socialist, and Liberal theories. All these theories explain that patriarchy is a set of social values that give men power to subdue women; however, these theories explain various ways to subjugate women.

In opposition to the patriarchal system, feminism supports equality between men and women (Macionis, 2012). The following are various theories of feminism that discuss how men use the patriarchy system to dominate and subdue women. The radical feminists are not unanimous on the basic principles of the system of patriarchy. However, most of them agree on one point: that it entails the expropriation of women's sexuality and bodies. The feminists firmly believe that patriarchy is so profoundly embedded in society that even a socialist revolution would fail to eradicate it. To achieve the goal of gender equality, society itself must strive to root out gender (Macionis, 2012). The use of modern reproductive technology may prove one conceivable approach to achieving this objective. The aim of this technology is to separate a woman's body from the process of childbearing. The radical feminists argue that the end of motherland will end the entire family system and liberate women, children, and men from the tyranny and oppression of family, gender, and sex itself (Dworkin, 1987). Radical feminists seek a gender free and egalitarian society, and such a society can only be attained if the patriarchal system is done away with. The debt of radical feminism is great to the issue of gender-based violence. Radical feminists are the pioneer theorists who advocated the concept that patriarchal norms support dominance over women, which results in violence against women (Millet, 1969; Griffen, 1971; Firestone, 1972; Brownmiller, 1975; Russell, 1975; Caputi, 1989).

Marxist feminism is a philosophical type of feminism that includes and extends Marxist theory. It analyzes the ways in which the capital system exploits women and the individual ownership of private property. Radical feminism differs from Marxist feminism. Later believes that women's suppression and subjugation do not originate from the patriarchal system; instead, it is capitalism that produces gender inequality, as it does not accord the same value to the labor of women (Walby 1990). Class inequality fundamentally produces gender inequality. Moreover, the Marxist theories use the lens of classism, not sexism, to exclude the ultimate cause of oppression and inequality among women. Both schools of thought (Radical Feminism and Marxist Feminism) highlight the role of power relations and emphasize that the stronger party will exploit the weaker party. The fundamental difference between both schools of thought is that the former considers the role of gender and patriarchy, while the later holds classism and capitalism responsible for violence against women.

Socialist feminism is rooted in socialist theory. According to socialist feminists, capitalism is an instrument for accumulating wealth and power in the hands of men, which results in strengthening patriarchy. If "domestic slavery" is to be rooted out, the family system created by capitalism must be altered or dismantled. This could be achieved by collective means of doing housework and rearing children (Macionis, 2012). This school of thought intensely criticizes capitalistic practices and institutions and believes that women's inequality is the outcome of patriarchy and capitalistic economic relations. They argue that this must undergo a change if women are to be liberated from the bondage of men (Chafetz, 1997). Socialist feminists encompass women's productive and reproductive labor.

1.1 Corpus Linguistics

Corpora have started to play a significant role in recent days in discourse analysis (Ahmed, 2023; Ahmed Fairclough, 2000; Flowerdew, 1997; Krishnamurthy, 1996; Mair, & Hundt, 2000; Piper, 2000; Teubert, 2000; McEnery, & Hardie, 2011; Tabbert, 2013). Corpus-based analysis affords analysts an opportunity to single out extended patterns of language that natural occur. Corpus linguists have a huge range of operations that may be employed and administered to analyze texts, e.g., frequency list, collocations, concordances, and dispersion plot.

This paper used a corpus linguistic approach to analyse data. This approach is the study of language with the assistance of a computer using vast collections of spoken or written texts (McEnery and Hardie, 2012). The study

uses a corpus-based approach that uses corpora to test, expound, and verify theories (Tognini-Bonelli, 2001) so that they can be validated, reined, or refuted (McEnery and Hardie, 2012). The irrelevant texts like headings were deleted (Mollin, 2007), and all the files were converted into txt files to make the data machine readable (McEnery et al., 2006). The present study employs WMatrix (Rayson, 2008) software for the purpose of analysis. This software analyses words in context, that is, how words are used in concordances. This procedure involves two stages: (i) quantitative identification of words based on information that tells how words are used in text; (ii) going beyond quantitative patterns that lead to functional interpretations of the words (Biber et al., 1998). This process of functional interpretations of the patterns leads to the socio-cultural environment of the text under analysis (Bednarek, 2006; Gabrielatos and Baker, 2008). Thus, words like murder, kill, sexual, rape and raped were investigated so that the patterns of how these words were associated with discourse might be discovered.

Concordances were examined in order to know how the above-mentioned words were used in context. Concordance is a collection of co-occurrences of words within a brief span of text (Sinclair, 1991). This process allows the researchers to search for a certain word or phrase used in specific environments. It means to investigate how a word or phrase typically co-occurs with other words or phrases to form meaning in the context of a text (Evison, 2010). Thus, the words stated above were searched for how they were used in concordances to examine their semantic prosody, which constitutes the “subtle element of attitudinal” and “semantic meaning” linked with these words (Sinclair, 2004). Below are a few studies that used corpus linguistic approach to investigate various phenomena. Karimullah (2020) examined political corpora comprising online Arabic and English to investigate the representation of women. Discursive similarities and differences that characterize two languages were highlighted. The representational categories found in each corpus were indexed based on the patterns of collocation. The analysis revealed that the way women were represented in various media outlets are portrayed with bias, and women are informed by their conception of agency.

Musa and Waseem (2015) investigated news columns published in a Pakistani English newspaper, the Dawn. They investigated how women are represented in the writings of male and female writers. Ant Conc 3.4.1 was used to analyze the data. Significant differences were discovered between the writings of both writers. The male journalistic writings portray women as more passive recipient of some benefits or violence from others. The male writer rarely discusses the active roles of women. Whereas in the writings of female journalists, women are shown more active and performing actions. Ali et al. (2020) used the text 'Antconc Software' (Anthony, 2007) to investigate oppression on Pakistani women. For this purpose, data were collected from Bapsi Sidhwa's novel *The Bride*. This novel is the story of a woman, namely Zaitoon, brought up in Lahore and married to a tribal man, Sakhi, by her foster father, Qasim. Zaitoon is persecuted and battered by her husband, even on an ordinary pretext. Ultimately, she quit her husband's home, chased, and slaughtered. The research aimed at discovering adjectives used to portray men and women and how these adjectives sketched patriarchy in the novel. Adjectives, e.g., arrogant, bloody, ferocious, cruel, inhuman, strong, and stubborn, were used to delineate male characters. Women were sketched with adjectives like dead, embarrassed, delicate, black, silent, shy, weeping, dainty, weak, bare, and dainty. The images of men and women drawn with adjectives pointed out that women were maltreated by men in Pakistan.

Shaheen (2017) used the *Corpus Linguistics software Wordsmith 6.0* to identify the national identity of Pakistan in Pakistani English newspapers. He identified what linguistic means, themes, and strategies were used to construct Pakistani identity. He conducted this study employing Discourse-Historical-Approach (DHA) given by Wodak. He discovered that Pakistan is portrayed as we-group and India are represented as another-group. Lexical items like nuclear, Kashmir and peace were used to construct Pakistani identity. Ahmed et al. (2020) employed critical stylistic analysis to investigate the linguistic construction of offender, victim, and crime in news stories on child sex abuse. The study made use of a qualitative research design. The news stories that appeared in print media were gleaned and analyzed qualitatively. The study revealed that linguistic devices, such as crime naming nouns and verbs, were used to construct the offender, perpetuating stereotypes and causing sympathy for the victim. The above studies show that there are a few studies that employed a corpus linguistic approach, particularly in the Pakistani context, to analyze the stories in the print media to ascertain patriarchy and gender-based violence. The present study aims at investigating how gender and violence are discursively represented in the discourse of English newspapers in Pakistan.

1.2 Research Questions

- a) How patriarchy and gender-based violence are linguistically constructed in English newspapers?
- b) What linguistic strategies are used in media discourse in terms of gender violence and patriarchy?

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design: Mixed-Methods

The present study employs a corpus-based approach to address the research questions. It combines qualitative analysis and quantitative data to unveil the discursive practices of discourses while using corpus tools. The underlying idea of employing mixed methods is that it provides sufficient research depth (Enosh, Tzafirir, & Stolovy, 2014). The corpus consisted newspaper crime stories and reports. These crime stories from five different English newspapers in Pakistan were selected. These stories were collected over a period of two years, i.e., 2017 and 2018. These news items were chosen from the five daily national newspapers. These newspapers are The Dawn, The Express Tribune, The News, The Nation, and The Daily Times. These papers enjoy national and international repute and have a wide readership.

2.2 Data Analysis

As the preset study harnessed a mixed methods research design, this included both qualitative and quantitative analysis. For the quantitative part of the analysis, computer-based software from Corpus Linguistics, WMatrix (Rayson, 2008), was used. To answer the research questions qualitatively, theories of feminism were used. The news stories on crime from various English newspapers were gathered from the years 2017- 2018. The nature of these news reports is violence against women. For the quantitative part of the analysis Corpus Linguistics software was employed. So, it seemed essential that a brief introduction of Corpus Linguistics and the software “WMatrix” be given here.

2.3 WMatrix

WMatrix is computer-based software. It was created by Paul Rayson. It can answer data in multiple ways. It can generate keyword list, concordance lists, and n-grams, which are very helpful to analyze and reduce the subjectivity of the researcher. It can also analyze the data systematically. The present study uses this software only to generate keywords lists and concordances.

First of all, a wordlist was produced with the help of software. This list helped to construct gender-based violence, which was explained with the help of theories of feminism. Later, the words were scrutinized, and verbs and nouns that referred to violence were sorted out. These words are like harass, battering, killing, honor killing, rape, assault, etc. These words are sometimes used as nouns and sometimes as verbs. The voice of the sentences was also scrutinized. Both active voice and passive voice were used to construct offenses. The reporters used passive voice when the concealment of the agent was required. An active voice was used when the perpetrator of violence was to be pointed out. The cutoff point for choosing a frequency limit was fourteen. It means that the chosen words must have been used in the corpus at least fourteen times. (To choose a word limit subjectively, see Stubbs, 2005). The word limit was not chosen automatically. It was the researchers who chose the word limit subjectively. The words that served as keys to constructing gender-based violence were manually extracted. The process of extracting words minimized the number of words and helped control analysis. The following were lexical items that construct violence: They were: murder (1619), killed (1087) rape (956), raped (668), sexual (626), violence (573), killing (561), injured (486), abuse (437), died (345), assault (323), assaulted (307), tortured (243), strangled (207), raping (187), and attacked (157). There were 13652 sentences in the corpus, which made 3, 72, 622 words. The frequency of the words was objectively extracted. These words offer the first stage for continuing the analysis.

After the words were chosen on the basis of frequency, the concordances of every chosen linguistic item were drawn and analyzed. The software presented the total concordances of every word. Then the examples given in the study were extracted randomly. For this purpose, the same software, WMatrix, was used. Concordances carry tremendous significance as they dish up the context in which that particular word was used.

3. Results: Construction of Gender-based Violence

There are total 16 words used in the corpus, which represent VAW. These words are used in the corpus in the form of verbs and nouns. The violence that these words constructed was sexual assault, harassment, murder, rape, acid burning, and domestic violence. These words were chosen only from the cases that were reported in the English print media during 2017 and 2018.

The women were afflicted with many kinds of violence. One of them is their murder. They were murdered for multiple reasons. They were murdered because they allegedly established sexual relations outside of marriage. They might be murdered by their husbands or any other member of their family. One reason for their killing is honor killing.

3.1 Honor Killing

Honor killers associate women's bodies with the honor of family. Men try to regulate, protect, and direct the women's sexuality. Men resort to the socio-cultural values of society to restrict women's freedom to guard family honor. According to these social values, family honor is embodied in women's bodies. So, women are bound to guard their chastity and virginity for men's honor. Following are the concordances and examples extracted with their help from the data to construct honor killing.

Export concordance
with tabs between keyword and left/right context (right mouse click on the link and save as a text file)
Note: this only saves the latest concordance - if you open a new window and run another concordance, then that one will be exported.

Change character width:

19 occurrences.		Extend context	
dead and his wife was injured in an	honor killing in Islampura on Sunday night	1	More Full
dead and his wife was injured in an	honor killing in Islampura on Sunday night	2	More Full
is wife and daughter in the name of	honor and son for being illegitimate child	3	More Full
004 and 2016 . Over 15,000 cases of	honor crimes were registered . There were	4	More Full
be right to kill her in the name of	honor ? Does such extreme action of a fami	5	More Full
tion of a family really reclaim its	honor in the society ? How many girls will	6	More Full
bad Police suspect it was a case of	honor killing ; husband still on the run E	7	More Full
nes her story and looks at brutal "	honor killings " in the Islamic country .	8	More Full
with her lover . These so-called "	honor killings " arerampant across Pakista	9	More Full
who are the main suspects in this "	honor killing " case . In another incident	10	More Full
to determine the exact number of "	honor killing " victims . Most of these ca	11	More Full
. Read more : Indian police arrest	honor killing gang " In Pakistan , it is n	12	More Full
tiespassed a stricter law to curb "	honor " crimes . It came right afterprotes	13	More Full
came right afterprotestsover the "	honor killing " of a prominentPakistani mo	14	More Full
entitled to pardon a murderer in "	honor killing " cases . The new law guaran	15	More Full
sing of a new law , the number of "	honor " crimes in Pakistan remained high .	16	More Full
thority to rule out the aspect of "	honor killing " from the murder case . Thi	17	More Full
riarchal society tends to condone "	honor killings . " In 2014 , US-based Pew	18	More Full
f 10 people in Pakistan justified "	honor killings " in some way . " The gover	19	More Full

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Table 1 Construction of Honor Killing in News Corpus

officials suspect could be an honour killing case . The couple was latter continue to rule on honour killing cases , other murders and st increasing child abuse , honour killing , and fake encounters . Four suspects involved in honour killing caught in Islamabad The , allegedly involved in an honour killing case in Karachi last month HANG:In what seems to be an honour killing case , a woman and her s murdered by her husband . Honour killing : Woman who burned daughter

Example 1: A woman arrested for burning her 16-year-old daughter alive for marrying without family consent in a so-called " honour killing, " the Express Tribune: January 28, 2018

Example 2: Four suspects involved in honour killing caught in Islamabad. The Dawn 25 Mar 2018

In the examples, honor-killing is used as a noun, and it constructs gender-based violence. When a woman is accused of developing extramarital or illicit relations, she does two acts. First, she violates the ownership rights of others resting in her body. Secondly, she challenges the values erected in the system of patriarchy. Patriarchy believes it is not a significant thing in honor-killing if a woman is guilty or not of having illicit sexual relations. The perception of the people matters. The honor of the family demands remedial action. When a woman brings shame, she must die to clean up and restore family honor. The male members usually defend the honor and display masculinity by killing the woman (Afzel et al., 2021; Watto, 2002). The police generally do not intervene in such

matters and declare them private matters (Falu, 2015; Nawaz, 2020). During two years (2017-2018), 125 women were butchered in the name of honor, and patriarchal values give men power to control women (Sultana, 2012; Rawat, 2014).

Women should be given an opportunity to answer the allegation of bringing shame to the family before taking the law into their hands and restoring family honor. Honor killing is not seen as a crime; instead, it is believed to be an appropriate and legitimate punishment for a woman who defiles family honor. If a woman defiles a family honor, the male member punishes her under the public pressure and the remarks that may be leveled against such a family (Ruane, 2000). If the family spares a woman, bad remarks like “beghairat” are leveled against it. Example 1 demonstrates that patriarchal culture is as powerful as even a mother burnt her daughter, who eloped away with her suitor and married him with her own heart. Radical feminism explains this kind of violence that men believe they can regulate and should regulate women’s sexuality.

3.2 Rape and Sexual Assault

The word rape has been used in two categories to construct gender-based violence. Rape as a noun and rape as a verb. This word occurs in the corpus 582 and 382 times respectively

Table 2: Construction of raped in newspapers

done house . The culprit allegedly raped her and fled a
 015 six women were kidnapped , four raped , three committed
 31 Jul 2017 After being repeatedly raped by a man who h
 the street . A next-door neighbour raped her at his resid
 claiming to have been assaulted or raped by one of the mo

Example 3: In 2015 six women were kidnapped, four raped, three committed suicide and six were murdered every day in Pakistan. The Express Tribune: July 06 , 2017

Example 4: 18 women claiming to have been assaulted or raped by one of the most influential figures. The Dawn; 24 Nov 2017

Example 3 shows the gravity of the violence, and example 4 shows how patriarchy is embedded in social values. Marxist feminism rightly points out that classism are responsible for gender-based violence. An

influential man has sexually victimized 18 women who must have belonged to a low class.

In a patriarchal society, women are raped or sexually assaulted for multiple reasons. Rape is wielded as a powerful instrument to show power and masculinity and is employed as a tool to punish women who refused the suitors' designs or might have thwarted these designs earlier and later developed relations with the same men. These men sexually assault such women or rape them in order to satisfy their egos. It is also used as a mechanism to take revenge for some wrong done by a male member of the family of the unfortunate woman. It is also a misplaced concept that women encourage, instigate, or invite men to rape them by their provocative behavior or dresses. The inherent idea behind sexual violence is primarily to exercise power, not sex. Some feminists view rape and intimidation as instruments in the hands of men to put control over women (Brownmiller, 1975; Basu & Ghosh, 2018).

Patriarchy explains rape in various ways. First, women enjoy sex; second, women merit rape; and third, men should demonstrate aggressive and assertive sexual behavior. Sex is forced on women through threats of violence, cultural expectation, economic circumstances, deception, and verbal insistence (Heise et al., 1995).

3.3 Intimate partner violence (IPV)

Intimate partners inflict violence on their spouses, and it is the most common form of violence. Women of all classes suffer from intimate partner violence. This form of violence normally occurs among husband and wife or X-husband and wife. Violence between partners may include sexual violence, psychological, economic, and physical violence (Jewekes, 2002). Women are subjected to loss of power, sexual harassment, and moral force (Coker et al., 2000; Zara & Gino, 2018). Marxist feminists believe that capitalism is solely responsible for violence against women. Women who are financially not dependent on their husbands are not subjected to violence.

resident of Ahmadabad, attacked his wife , Naila , with a knife and fled the	429	More Full
on the spot , he said . Man murders wife , stepdaughter in Faisalabad Police	430	More Full
ISALABAD:A man allegedly killed his wife and stepdaughter within Chak Jhumra	431	More Full
not like Rubina and would force his wife to send the girl to her in-laws home	432	More Full
suspect confessed to murdering his wife and step-daughter . He said the culp	433	More Full
d two women . He divorced his first wife , while the other left him along wit	434	More Full
Arrest was made on the complaint of wife Express Tribune Sep19 , 2018 KARACHI	435	More Full
pdughter goes public Shah says his wife is not the real daughter of his ex ,	436	More Full
On Friday , Syed Waris Ali Shah and wife Syeda Sameera held a press conferenc	437	More Full
ul Haq . Shah said that his present wife Sameera had fled home due to her abu	438	More Full
: A man arrested for murder of his wife was allegedly found dead with his th	439	More Full
y worker , had allegedly killed his wife Hina over domestic issues , last wee	440	More Full
lainant claimed she was still Shahs wife and under Shariah , marrying the ste	441	More Full
ars . However , the accused and his wife obtained bail before arrest and clar	442	More Full
religious injunctions . His second wife , who was also present at the news c	443	More Full
Saturday . According to IO , Shahs wife was sent to Abbottabad jail the same	444	More Full
ut failed to arrest him . Man kills wife , daughter for 'honour' in Sanghar P	445	More Full
oke into his house and poisoned his wife . But the police said the circumstan	446	More Full
n his report to the police said his wife was in her room while his children w	447	More Full
and injured Muhammad Hussain , his wife Nasim Bibi and sister-in-law Allah M	448	More Full
ack magic on him . Dr Nazir and his wife , Robina , were found murdered by fi	449	More Full
ifle) from the suspect . Man kills wife , twin step daughters in Sargodha Re	450	More Full
23 , 2018 SARGODHA:A man killed his wife and twin step daughters in Sargodha	451	More Full
o Shaukat used an axe to murder his wife and his step daughters . After murde	452	More Full
inhuman treatment and murder of his wife , Najma Shah , 40 , whose body with	453	More Full
NAUDERO : A man allegedly shot his wife over a domestic dispute in Hassan Wa	454	More Full
wife to sexual abuse . Man tortures wife to death The Nation : September 30 ,	455	More Full
AD - A man tortured his 53-year-old wife , mother of five , to death over a f	456	More Full
episode and he often would ask his wife about his daughter . He again asked	457	More Full
vestigation . Man allegedly poisons wife to death in Faisalabad Couple used t	458	More Full
ALABAD:A man allegedly poisoned his wife to death in Khurrianwala police stat	459	More Full

Table 3 Construction of intimate partners violence in corpus

A young man shot dead his estranged wife before committing suicide over some
n , was found guilty of killing his wife Zubaida by setting her ablaze in the
ck district on Sunday shot dead his wife , daughters and injured his son in M
ces said the accused had killed his wife in the name of honour . They said th
e of the night but did not find his wife in the room . He said he went to ano
not like Rubina and would force his wife to send the girl to her in-laws home
her husband , he stated . Man kills wife over domestic dispute SIALKOT - A ma

Example 5: Police claimed Irfan attacked his wife Rabi with an axe over a domestic issue. The Dawn: 17 Sep 2017

Example 6: A woman was set ablaze allegedly by her ex-husband over a domestic dispute at Kahna on Saturday. Police said. The Express Tribune October 21, 2018

In these examples, it is observed that wives are targets of various kinds of violence at the hands of present or former husbands.

The word wife appears 1007 times in the Corpus. These women have been subjected to violence at the hands of their X-husbands or their present husbands. The violence women suffered mainly stemmed from domestic issues. First, both partners exchanged hot words in almost the majority of the incident, and eventually women became the victims of violence. The above examples of concordances amply showed it, and the textual examples extracted from the data with the help of concordances revealed that the men persecuted them just to satisfy their whims.

3.4 Acid Attacks

In Pakistan, acid attacks have been on the rise. Acid attacks are committed deliberately, and the purpose is to disfigure the victims. Such violence is committed generally in South Asia (Restrepo-Bernal et al., 2014). Jilted lovers and refused marriage proposals are responsible for such violence (Ismail et al., 2020). This violence is usually committed by throwing acid on the victims' faces (Johanssen & Garrisi, 2019). Dowry may be another reason for acid burning (Watt & Zimmerman, 2002).

Table 4 Construction of violence related to acid attacks in corpus

over which , they made her drink acid , which eventually resulted in her r and leg . Drug addicted man pours acid down wives throat Daily Times : Kainat than the burns caused by the acid that left her unable to speak , the ts , Nabi alleged , had also thrown acid on his daughter . Nabi also alleged st women every year , from rape and acid attacks to sexual assault , kidnappi

Example 7: Pakistan, home to roughly 190 million people, sees thousands of cases of violence against women every year, from rape and acid attacks to sexual assault, kidnappings and so-called "honour killings." Pakistan Today: May 05, 2017

Example 8: What was even more painful for Kainat than the burns caused by the acid that left her unable to speak. Pakistan Today: JULY 30, 2017

These concordances show that women have been subject to acid burning and, too, by the husbands or in-laws.

3.5 Incest

When a sister, daughter or niece is sexually assaulted by her brother, father, maternal uncle, or paternal uncle, such violence is called incestuous violence.

Table 5 Construction of violence related to acid attacks in corpus

prison for subjecting his teenage daughter to a sexual assault . The court ha
n had earlier subjected her other daughter to sexual abuse . She also said th
n allegedly raped his 16-year-old daughter for three months in the Pano Dheri
ed that the suspect had raped his daughter . The incidents came in the wake
prison for subjecting his teenage daughter to a sexual assault . The court ha

Example 9: A sessions court in Karachi had sentenced a man to 12 years in prison for subjecting his teenage daughter to a sexual assault. The Express Tribune: April 11, 2018

Example 10: a man allegedly raped his 16-year-old daughter for three months in the Pano Dheri Village. The News: 13-02-2018

Various young women have been victims of sexually assaulted by their blood relations like father and paternal/maternal uncles. But such offenders are seldom punished due to pressure they bring on the victims or their mothers. This is a glaring example of patriarchy.

3.6 Dowry Related Violence

Dowry means an amount or things (household goods, etc.) which the family of a bride pays or gives at the time or before marriage to the groom so that the daughter could be married off and she could live honorably with her in-laws. If the parents of the bride do not meet the expectations of the groom or his parents, the bride is usually harassed or sometimes murdered. Such obnoxious violence is prevalent in South Asia, particularly India and Pakistan (Priyanka & Jayoti, 2014).

The screenshot shows the Wmatrix software interface with a concordance table for the word 'dowry'. The table has two main columns: '26 occurrences' and 'Extend context'. Each row contains a snippet of text from a source, the word 'dowry', and a link to view more context. The sources include news articles from Pakistan Today and The Dawn.

26 occurrences	Extend context
istered a murder case against him . Dowry : a unique form of gender-based viol	1 More Full
nique form of gender-based violence Dowry is an amount of property brought by	2 More Full
rmal or customary . In my opinion , dowry is one form of normative GBV that is	3 More Full
societies have seemingly evolved , dowry orjahezis still practised in most ge	4 More Full
torians trace back the tradition of dowry to thekanyadanacconcept along with th	5 More Full
law titled , the Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa Dowry , Bridal Gift and Marriage Functions	6 More Full
ask or force the brides family for dowry . If they still do , they shall be l	7 More Full
amount , it does not clearly define dowry as a malpractice . A more desperate	8 More Full
he draft bill presented for banning dowry . Obviously , a great amount of crit	9 More Full
on the implementation of the law . Dowry is a cult , a malpractice that has b	10 More Full
e almost 2,000 cases reported about dowry deaths per year ? Why does Pakistan	11 More Full
stan still have the highest rate of dowry death at 2.45 per 100,000 women ? La	12 More Full
emotional abuse , honour killings , dowry violence , acid throwing , forced ma	13 More Full
ties . Woman poisoned to death over dowry The Dawn 25 Sep 2018 STALKOT : A wom	14 More Full
sday for not bringing their desired dowry . Aneeba Shehzadi , 26 , belonged to	15 More Full
her as punishment for not bringing dowry of their choice and administered her	16 More Full
d already given her in-laws a heavy dowry , including gold ornaments and costl	17 More Full
emotional abuse , honour killing , dowry and inheritance related murder , aci	18 More Full
oom on wedding day in Khanewal over dowry dispute Wedding guests said a scuffl	19 More Full
sts said a scuffle erupted over the dowry and the bride 's brother shot her hu	20 More Full
ted argument with Muzaffar over the dowry and shot him dead .. Disabled woman	21 More Full
ago and the woman did not bring the dowry according to the expectations of her	22 More Full
in the country . Woman hanged over dowry issue The Dawn : 01 Aug 2017 A woman	23 More Full
hanged to death by her in-laws over dowry in 269/HR , Fort Abbas , on Monday .	24 More Full
d to beat her for bringing a little dowry . Neighbours also told police that F	25 More Full
ysical torture for not bringing the dowry items they had demanded from her par	26 More Full

Table 6 Construction of dowry related violence in corpus

istered a murder case against him . Dowry : a unique form of
ask or force the brides family for dowry . If they still do , they shall
ed argument with Muzaffar over the dowry and shot him dead ..
d to beat her for bringing a little dowry . Neighbours also told police that F

Example 11: Police investigation revealed that Fatima’s in-laws used to beat her for bringing a little dowry. The Nation: MARCH 21, 2017

Example 12: Dowry: a unique form of gender-based violence. Pakistan Today: MARCH 21, 2018

These examples construct gendered-based violence. A woman was married off; she failed to bring the desired amount of dowry and became the victim of her in-laws’ ire and had to lose her life. All this was done with the connivance of their husbands and male members of the family.

3.7 Violence Related to the Birth of Female Infants

Example 13: A man allegedly poisoned his wife to death. 28-year-old Naveeda Bibi had married Amjad five years ago but the couple did not have any child. They quarreled over this issue.

In patriarchal societies, people give preference to male-babies in countries like Pakistan and India. Women who fail to give birth to a male baby have to suffer from violence at the hands of their husbands, in-laws or both (Khattak, 2014). This type of violence is common in India, China, Sub-Saharan countries, and Pakistan (Miller, 2001). These women were victimized on a gender basis for giving birth to female babies.

3.8 Violence Related to Rejection of Marriage Proposal

To marry is a private affair, but in Pakistan, marriage is not contracted between two individuals. Instead, the members of two families are involved in it. Besides it, women particularly cannot decide to marry of their own choice. If a woman ever tries to marry or has married of her own choice, she has to pay a heavy price for it, which is usually her death or the death of both. Likewise, if a woman rejects or refuses to accept the marriage proposal of her suitor or elder of family, she has to suffer from a variety of violence ranging from emotional violence to murder (Ismail et al., 2020). In the example in the table of concordance, Asma Rani, a law student from Lahore, rejected the marriage proposal of her classmate. She was brutally and publically stabbed 23 times on Davis Road, Lahore. Similarly, an uncle victimized his niece, who refused to marry his son.

46	More	Full
47	More	Full
48	More	Full
49	More	Full
50	More	Full
51	More	Full
52	More	Full
53	More	Full
54	More	Full
55	More	Full
56	More	Full
57	More	Full
58	More	Full
59	More	Full
60	More	Full
61	More	Full
62	More	Full
63	More	Full
64	More	Full
65	More	Full
66	More	Full
67	More	Full
68	More	Full
69	More	Full
70	More	Full
71	More	Full
72	More	Full
73	More	Full
74	More	Full
75	More	Full
76	More	Full

Table 8 Construction of Violence Related to Rejection of Marriage proposal in corpus

he targeted Asma Rani after she rejected his marriage proposal . Asma
 cing her to marry his son but she rejected the proposal . Yes , an initial
 landlord is behind the murder . Rejected suitor The accused murderer of
 ical college student for refusing marriage proposal , had fled to Saudi Ara
 daughters when they rejected his marriage proposal . The attacker fled insta

Example 13: Initial police investigations suggest the killer attacked the mother and her daughters when they rejected his marriage proposal. The Nation November 24, 2018 LAHORE

Example 14: Allegedly, he targeted Asma Rani after she rejected his marriage proposal.

In such cases women become victims of violence because men believe it is their (men’s) right to decide the marriage of women of the family. If a suitor is rejected, his manhood is piqued badly and it entails violence.

3.9 Jirga/ Panchayet Related Gender-Based Violence

The patriarchal system does not accord rights to women. Whenever, in Pakistan, it is discovered that a man is having illicit relations with a woman, the aggrieved family approaches the punchayat. The punchayat, in order to punish the suitor, orders that his sister or daughter should be dealt with in the same manner. In this way, the innocent woman becomes the scapegoat who has to suffer for the wrongs of a male member of the family. This is particularly true. The irony is this: the Pakistani judicial system does not put up a barrier against such gender-based violence. If the members of such punchayat or executioners of the orders of such punchayat are ever prosecuted, they are exonerated at some stage later.

Wmatrix4: KIIC context results jirgas

You are logged in to Wmatrix4 as: culahorerafa

Warning: Wmatrix4 will be retired on 1st March 2023. Please consider switching to use Wmatrix5 as soon as possible. If you are a student using Wmatrix4 then please talk to your module leader for more information.

Export concordance
with tabs between keyword and left/right context (right mouse click on the link and save as a text file)
Note: this only saves the latest concordance - if you open a new window and run another concordance, then that one will be exported.

Change character width: 80 Go

14 occurrences.		Extend context	
017 IT is unfortunate that illegal jirgas	have usurped judicial functions and	1 More	Full
t that flouting the law by holding jirgas	will not be tolerated . Despite a 2	2 More	Full
ite a 2004 Sindh High Court ban on jirgas	, the latter continue to rule on ho	3 More	Full
ise , the state must clamp down on jirgas	, if only to safeguard victims who	4 More	Full
ith stories of couples punished by jirgas	regularly published in Sindh delli	5 More	Full
justice systems of panchayats and jirgas	in sync with the juvenile justice s	6 More	Full
lling : Bodies of couple killed on jirgas	orders exhumed After exchange of ho	7 More	Full
. Often running their parties like jirgas	, politicians have themselves been	8 More	Full
em and are dealt with by village " jirgas	" or councils , often in a manner t	9 More	Full
murder . They also demanded ban on jirgas	, elimination of cruel practice of	10 More	Full
, broken criminal justice system , jirgas	that exclude and degrade women and	11 More	Full
an act of honour killing ; CM says jirgas	are not acceptable The incident spa	12 More	Full
Karachi is not a tribal area where jirgas	are held . SSP West Mohammed Younis	13 More	Full
litan city not a tribal area where jirgas	are held . I would not allow such k	14 More	Full

Table 9 Gender Based Violence by Jirgas/ Panchayets in corpus

lling : Bodies of couple killed on Jirgas orders exhumed After exchange of ho
 Karachi is not a tribal area where jirgas are held . SSP West Mohammed
 Younis
 017 IT is unfortunate that illegal jirgas have usurped judicial functions and

Example 15: Bodies of couple killed on Jirgas orders exhumed After exchange of hot words. The Dawn : 01 Jul 2017

Example 16: Middle-aged woman gang-raped at panchayat. The Dawn March 18, 2018

3.10 Gender-Base Violence Due to Property

Wmatrix4: KIIC context results property

You are logged in to Wmatrix4 as: culahorerafa

Warning: Wmatrix4 will be retired on 1st March 2023. Please consider switching to use Wmatrix5 as soon as possible. If you are a student using Wmatrix4 then please talk to your module leader for more information.

Export concordance
with tabs between keyword and left/right context (right mouse click on the link and save as a text file)
Note: this only saves the latest concordance - if you open a new window and run another concordance, then that one will be exported.

Change character width: 80 Go

121 occurrences.		Extend context	
cyclists on Wednesday shot dead a	property dealer in Samanabad . Police said	1 More	Full
came to the office of 50-year-old	property dealer Malik Naeem , sprayed him w	2 More	Full
police that his brother had some	property dispute with a local , Khurram Sha	3 More	Full
scribed as a family dispute over	property in Gulistan-i-Jauhar on Thursday e	4 More	Full
the incident was the outcome of a	property dispute . Child sexual abuse A new	5 More	Full
eerRafique , son of a millionaire	property dealer , and taken him into custod	6 More	Full
ce of Zina , and Offences Against	Property (Enforcement of Hudood) Ordinanc	7 More	Full
ions and not cause harm to public	property . It is worrisome that some people	8 More	Full
vehicles , so , they were public	property . Talking to the media , Zainabs f	9 More	Full
d to not damage public or private	property . However , he expressed dissatisfi	10 More	Full
our of a crowd is not an emergent	property of the crowd but is a result of li	11 More	Full
for the damage done to the public	property . The parents of youngsters should	12 More	Full
ernment to safeguard the life and	property of the people . He said though suc	13 More	Full
sible for protecting the life and	property of people but unfortunately the au	14 More	Full
for bringing former Evacuee Trust	Property Board (ETPB) chairman Asif Hashm	15 More	Full
uiet the police made it a case of	property dispute , while parents of the vic	16 More	Full
ents whom he tutored at a private	property , officials and activists said . T	17 More	Full
death by his relatives over some	property dispute here on Wednesday in Gujja	18 More	Full
with his nephew Nauman over some	property . On Wednesday , Ashiq and Nauman	19 More	Full
hile no casualty or damage to the	property was reported . Nurse found dead ne	20 More	Full

Example: A man and his wife were killed over a property dispute during a jirga in Sherpao area. Express tribune:

November 28 , 2017

Example 17: Man kills sister over property dispute The Dawn: 24 Feb 2018

Men, in a patriarchal society associate their authority with land. They do not want that their land should be divided among female persons of the family. The division of land usually becomes the cause of gender-based violence in which women have to lose their lives.

4. Conclusion

Gender-based violence originates from the patriarchal social system. Violence has been used by men as an instrument to suppress and dominate women. Gender-based violence, say feminist theorists, is a direct result of the patriarchal system. To understand gender-based violence appropriately in Pakistan, it is essential to understand patriarchy. Patriarchy is characterized by the socio-cultural norms and values of society. These socio-cultural norms and values are deeply rooted in Pakistani society, and they determine women's status in Pakistan. This is why a variety of violence, e.g., honor killing, psychological, emotional, rape, sexual harassment, battering, killing, dowry, property related violence, and acid burning are directed against women. The sole underpinning of the violence of patriarchy and not by sticking to patriarchal norms, men feel disadvantaged and their egos are hurt.

Structural violence that is encouraged by state institutes also patronizes gender-based violence. Gender-based violence is usually ignored on the premise that it is a private matter, and in rural and tribal areas, Jirga and panchayat are composed of men and they uphold patriarchal norms by persecuting women.

Violence against women is primarily an infringement of human rights. Such laws should not only be constituted but also not implemented to protect women's rights. The judicial system should be activated, and law enforcement agencies should not treat gender-based violence as a private matter. Women's empowerment from social, political, and economic point of view may help weaken the patriarchal system.

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